

New Triterpenes from *Barringtonia acutangula* Gaertn

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Besides β -sitosterol, stigmaterol-3 β -O-D-glucoside, oleanolic and barringtogenic acids two new triterpene acids, viz acutangolic and tangulic acids were isolated from the leaves of *Barringtonia acutangula*. From spectral data and chemical reactions, acutangolic and tangulic acid were shown to be 2 α ,3 β ,18 β -trihydroxy-olean-12-ene-28-oic acid and 2 α ,3 β ,18 β -trihydroxy-olean-12-ene-23,28-dioic acid respectively.

IN view of its reputation as an indigenous drug¹, many investigators studied the chemical constituents of *Barringtonia acutangula*. From various parts of this interesting tree, the isolation of a number of new polyhydric alcohols of β -amyrin series and hydroxy carboxylic acids of the olean-12-ene series (Table 1) prompted us to extend this investigation to the leaves as well.

gives rise to a diacetate (V), C₃₄H₅₂O₇, M⁺, 572, m.p. 189–90°, [α]_D–35° and a diacetylmethyl ester (VI), C₃₅H₅₄O₇, M⁺ 586, m.p. 219–20°, [α]_D–8°. The diacetate (V) as well as its methyl ester (VI) exhibit a prominent hydroxyl peak at 3540 cm⁻¹, indicating that one of the three hydroxyls remains unacetylated. Methyl acutangulate (IV) consumed 1 mole of mono-perphthalic acid in 168 h. resembling methyl oleanolate¹⁶

TABLE 1—OLEAN-12-ENES FROM *BARRINGTONIA ACUTANGULA* GAERTN

Sl. No.	Compound	Position of hydroxyls	Extra functions CH ₃	Source	Ref.
1.	Barringtogenol B	3 β , 16 α , 22 α , 28	21 β –OCOC=CH–CH ₃	Fruits	2,3
2.	Barringtogenol C	3 β , 16 α , 21 β , 22 α , 28	—	Fruits	4,5
3.	Barringtogenol D	3 β , 22 α , 28	16 α –21 α oxide	Fruits	5,6
4.	Barringtogenic acid	2 α , 3 β	23,28–(COOH) ₂	Fruits	7
5.	Barrigenic acid	2 α , 3 β , 19 β	23,28–(COOH) ₂	Fruits	8
6.	Tanginol	3 β , 6 β , 7 β , 16 β , 23, 28	—	Heartwood	9,10
7.	Barringtonic acid	2 α , 3 β , 6 β	23,28–(COOH) ₂	Heartwood	11
8.	Barringtogenol E	3 β , 16 α , 28	21 β , 22 α –(OCOC ₂ H ₅) ₂	Branchwood	12
9.	Barrinic acid	2 α , 3 β , 19 α	23,28–(COOH) ₂	Branchwood	13,14
10.	Neutral sapogenols	—	—	Bark	15

From the acidic fraction of the ethyl acetate extract of the leaves, two new triterpene carboxylic acids, designated as acutangolic and tangulic acids (III, XII), were isolated besides the well known sterols, β -sitosterol, and stigmaterol-3 β -O-D-glucoside and the triterpenes, oleanolic and barringtogenic acids (I, II). The two new acids were separated by fractional crystallisation of their acetate mixture, using acetone-benzene, the acetate of tangulic acid crystallising out first. The pure acids were secured by hydrolysis of the pure acetates.

Acutangulic acid (III) crystallised from methanol as colourless short needles, m. p. 290–91°, [α]_D+15°. It is a trihydroxy triterpene monocarboxylic acid, C₃₀H₄₈O₅, IR : 3550 cm⁻¹(OH), 1695 cm⁻¹(COOH);

(I, R₃=Me), but the double bond could not be hydrogenated over Adam's catalyst. It contained a *trans*-glycol system (1 mole of periodate in 8 h.)¹⁷ and can be located at 2 α , 3 β -positions on the basis of NMR and mass spectral data.

Mass spectral fragmentation of diacetyl acutangulic acid (v) as well as methyl ester (VI) furnished the expected RDA fragments¹⁸ at *m/e* 264(50); 278(80) (VII) and at *m/e* 308(5), 308(10) (VIII), suggesting that the hindered hydroxyl might be in D or E ring and not in A or B. The hydrogen geminal to 2 α -acetoxyl appeared as an ill-defined quartet at δ 5.05, 5.12, 5.20, 5.28 J=4, 9 Hz and the proton geminal to 3 β -acetoxyl as a doublet at δ 4.8, 4.9 J=9 Hz; in close agreement with a number of 2 α , 3 β -dihydroxy triterpenes¹⁹.

- I : $R_1 = H, R_2 = CH_3$
 II : $R_1 = OH, R_2 = COOH$
 III : $R = H, R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = COOH$
 IV : $R = H, R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = COOMe$
 V : $R = Ac, R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = COOH$
 VI : $R = Ac, R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = COOMe$
 XII : $R = H, R_1 = R_2 = COOH$
 XIII : $R = Ac, R_1 = R_2 = COOH$
 XIV : $R = Ac, R_1 = R_2 = COOMe$

The third hydroxyl could not be acetylated even under forced conditions (with perchloric acid) and diacetylmethyl acutangulate (VI) exhibited a broad singlet at δ 2.60 (partially exchanging with D_2O) indicating its tertiary character. It even exhibits an unusual resistance to pyridine-chromium trioxide. Even after prolonged action with $AcOH-CrO_3$ or Jones's reagent²⁰, the hydroxyl remained unaffected giving rise, instead, to an $\alpha : \beta$ -unsaturated 11-keto-diacetylmethyl acutangulate (IX), $C_{35}H_{52}O_8$, m.p. 166°, IR $3540cm^{-1}$ (OH) and $1650 cm^{-1}$ ($\alpha : \beta$ -unsaturated six membered ring ketone).

- VII $R = H (CH_3)$
 VIII $R = CH_3$
 XIV $R = COOH (CH_3)$
 IX $R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = COOMe$
 X $R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = COOMe$
 XI $R_1 = R_2 = COOH$
 XV $R_1 = R_2 = COOMe$
 XVI $R_1 = R_2 = COOH$

The tertiary hydroxyl in diacetyl methylacutangulate (VI), on the other hand, underwent facile dehydration with $POCl_3$ -pyridine to yield diacetylmethylanhydroacutangulate (X), $C_{35}H_{52}O_8$, m.p. 180-83°, $[\alpha]_D +116^\circ$, which contained a *s-cis* diene system [UV 246 nm (log ϵ 4.20) with a shoulder at 252 nm], the newly formed double bond conjugating with 12 : 13 double bond. The NMR spectrum of the new diene contained an additional olefinic proton at δ 5.43s in addition to the common 12 C-H, at δ 5.50 m. The facile formation of the *s-cis* diene makes it necessary to locate the tertiary hydroxyl at C-18 and the anhydro compound to

contain a $\Delta^{12,18}$ diene system (X). The structure of the anhydro compound suggests that it could be identical with diacetyl methyl anhydroarjunate, a derivative of arjunic acid from *Terminalia arjuna*²¹. Comparison with an authentic sample established their identity beyond doubt (mmp and superimposable IR).

The anhydroacutangulate (X) could be readily isomerised with chloroformic HCl to the corresponding $\Delta^{11,13(18)}$ diene (XI), which was found to be identical with an authentic sample of diacetylmethyl dehydro-maslinate. This provided additional support to structure III for acutangulic acid.

Information regarding the stereochemistry of this 18-hydroxyl was next sought through lactonisation using $HBr-AcOH$ ²². Acutangulic acid (III) or its diacetate (V) always afforded a mixture of compounds which could not be resolved. If the hydroxyl is 18- α oriented, lactonisation would be facile and a single product could be expected. Since the reaction was slow and a mixture of products was obtained, it is presumed that the D/E rings are *cis*-fused as in oleanolic acid (I) and 18-OH is β -oriented. On this basis, acutangulic acid (III) is assigned the structure 2 α , 3 β , 18 β -trihydroxy-olean-12-ene-28-oic acid.

The co-occurring tangulic acid (XII) crystallised from methanol as colourless, tiny prisms, m.p. 310-12°, $[\alpha]_D +35^\circ$, was isolated as its acetate in low yield (0.008%). It is a trihydroxy triterpene dicarboxylic acid, $C_{30}H_{46}O_7$, giving rise to a diacetate (XIII), $C_{34}H_{50}O_9$, m.p. 272-74°, $[\alpha]_D -15^\circ$, IR : $3560 cm^{-1}$ (OH) and a dimethyl ester diacetate (XIV), $C_{36}H_{54}O_9$, m.p. 168-69°, $[\alpha]_D +5^\circ$, IR: $3560 cm^{-1}$ (OH). Both the diacetate (XIII) and its dimethyl ester (XIV) exhibit a sharp and prominent peak at $3560 cm^{-1}$ and the broad band from $3500 - 3350 cm^{-1}$ of the parent tangulic acid disappeared, indicating that one of the three hydroxyls is sterically hindered and remains unacetylated.

The NMR spectra and mass spectral fragmentations clearly indicated its close relationship with acutangulic acid (III). The RDA fragments at m/e 264(15), 278(30) (VII), carry the single resistant hydroxyl as in acutangulic acid derivative (V, VI). The fragments at m/e 338(10), 352(40) (XV) clearly show that A/B unit of tangulic acid (XII) contains two acylable hydroxyls besides carboxylic function. Periodate titration (1 mole in 8 hr), confirmed the presence of $\alpha : \beta$ -*trans* diequatorial glycol system as in acutangulic acid (III).

That tangulic acid (XII) is a dicarboxylic acid, unlike acutangulic acid (III), was borne out by the two singlets at δ 3.64 (3H) and 3.76 (3H) in the NMR of diacetyldimethyltangulate (XIV). The position of the carboxyls could be surmised somewhat by the chemical shifts of the C-methyls [δ 0.717 (C_{20}); 1.30 (C_{24})] to be the same [δ 0.717 at C-23 and 28].

The coupling constants of protons on carbons carrying the acetoxy groups suggest a *trans*-glycol system at

C-2 and C-3 in the molecule. The 2β -hydrogen appears as a multiplet at δ 5.42 slightly more deshielded than in the case of diacetylmethyl acutangulate (VI) (δ 5.00), probably due to the presence of a carbomethoxy function at C-23 in the former compound; while the 3α -hydrogen appears as a doublet at δ 4.88, 5.05d; $J=10$ Hz. Further, as in diacetylmethyl acutangulate (VI), the NMR showed a broad singlet at δ 2.65, integrating for one proton. This has been assigned to the sterically hindered hydroxyl. The NMR does not also show any peaks between δ 2.80 and 4.00 assignable to a hydrogen geminal to a secondary hydroxyl, suggesting this hydroxyl to be tertiary, which was borne out by its chemical reactions.

Diacetyl tangulic acid (XIII) resisted $\text{Py}\cdot\text{CrO}_3$ oxidation but gave the 11-keto derivative (XVI), $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_{10}$, m.p. 165-68°, UV 256 (4.12) nm, IR: 3540 cm^{-1} (OH), 1650 cm^{-1} (α : β -unsaturated six membered ring ketone), thus showing that the hindered hydroxyl is resistant to esterification as well as oxidation, confirming its tertiary character as in acutangulic acid (III).

When refluxed with POCl_3 -Py for 3 hr, dehydration was smooth and the anhydro-compound (XVII) was secured as colourless needles, $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_8$, m.p. 178-79°, $[\alpha]_D -108^\circ$, UV 246 (4.02) nm and in this respect simulates the behaviour of the corresponding anhydro-compound of acutangulic acid, indicating the presence of a *cis*-heteroannular diene system. So, it is surmised that the tertiary hydroxyl is at the 18-position as in acutangulic acid and from analogy it can be considered that its stereochemistry is also 18 β .

These two triterpenes (III), XII) contain a hydroxyl each in a very unusual position namely C-18, not noticed so far except in glycerhaetic acid. The biogenetic origin of this 18-hydroxyl is not clear but it might have arisen through the 18, 19 or 13, 18 epoxide from the corresponding germanicol or δ -amyirin type of triterpenes.

Experimental

All mps are uncorrected. The IR spectra were run on Perkin-Elmer 237 Grating machine in nujol and UV on Beckmann DB-G spectrophotometer in ethanol unless otherwise stated. Silicagel C has been used for thin-layer chromatography.

The dry leaf powder (5 Kg) of *Barringtonia acutangula* was successively extracted with petroleum ether, ethyl acetate and alcohol in a Soxhlet apparatus.

Petroleum ether extract: Complete solvent removal yielded a dark green viscous residue (30 g). To remove the waxes, it was repeatedly dissolved in warm alcohol, cooled and filtered. The alcoholic solution (750 ml) was concentrated under vacuum and

allowed to stand over-night at room temp when a pale greenish yellow solid (25 g) separated. It was dissolved in chloroform (15 ml) and chromatographed over a column of alumina (20 g). Fractions 3-8 (hexane) were evaporated and crystallised from methanol to give colourless tiny crystals (0.2 g) of an unidentified fatty acid ester, m.p. 85-88°; LB test -ve and Solkowski's reaction -ve; IR: 1735, 1250 and 780 cm^{-1} . Fractions 9-20 (hexane-benzene, 8:2) gave on evaporation a pale yellow residue which crystallised from methanol as colourless needles of β -sitosterol (0.6 g), m.p. 136-37°, $[\alpha]_D -36^\circ$; acetate, m.p. 126-28°, $[\alpha]_D -39^\circ$. Fractions 31-38 (hexane-benzene, 1:1) were mixed, evaporated and the residue crystallised from methanol as colourless needles, of β -amyirin, (0.2 g), m.p. 197-98°, $[\alpha]_D +88^\circ$; acetate, m.p. 238-39°, $[\alpha]_D +84^\circ$.

Fractions 21-30 (hexane-benzene, 1:1) were mixed and crystallised from methanol to give β -sitosterol (0.8 g), m.p. 135-37°, fractions 41-55 (benzene-ethyl acetate, 8:2) were evaporated and the residue gave oleanolic acid crystallising from methanol/chloroform as colourless needles (0.95 g), m.p. 306-08°, $[\alpha]_D +74^\circ$; methyl ester, m.p. 196-98°, $[\alpha]_D +62^\circ$; methyl ester acetate, m.p. 221-22°, $[\alpha]_D +55^\circ$.

Ethyl acetate extract: The alcoholic solution of the residue (60 g) from this extract was treated with lead acetate to remove the tannins. The tannin and lead free solution, on concentration under vacuum furnished a pale yellow solid (15 g). It was separated into neutral and alkali soluble portions by 3% aq. KOH. The neutral portion (1.5 g) was crystallised twice from methanol when stigmasterol-3 β -O-D(+)-glucoside came out as colourless tiny needles (0.5 g), m.p. 264-65°, $[\alpha]_D +39^\circ$; positive L.B. and Molisch tests. Hydrolysis with 8% alcoholic H_2SO_4 afforded stigmasterol, m.p. 170-72°, $[\alpha]_D -41^\circ$; acetate, m.p. 141-42°. The hydrolysate showed only glucose (R_f 0.18, n-butanol-acetic acid-water, 4:1:5), identified by co-paper chromatography with an authentic sample of D(+)-glucose.

The mother liquors from stigmasterol-3 β -O-D(+)-glucoside were evaporated and the residue (1.0 g) was chromatographed over a column of silica gel (8 g) set in hexane. Hexane-benzene (1:1) gave β -sitosterol (0.3 g) on evaporation, while chloroform-methanol (8:2) eluate gave a small quantity of the above glucoside.

Careful fractional crystallisation of the acid fraction (5.0 g) from chloroform and methanol, gave a mixture of compounds III and XII (2.5 g). The mixture was acetylated (Ac_2O /pyridine, 100°, 3 hr) and crystallised from acetone, the acetate of the former being more sparingly soluble. Hydrolysis with 4% alcoholic alkali gave compounds XII (0.4 g) and III (1.2 g).

The filtrates from compounds XII and III were evaporated and the residue (2.0 g) chromatographed over a column of silica gel (12 g). Benzene eluate gave

oleanolic acid (0.6 g) while chloroform-methanol (9:1) eluate gave a small quantity of compound III (0.1 g). Chloroform-methanol (7:3) eluate gave compound II (0.1 g).

Tangulic acid (XII): Crude tangulic acid was acetylated with $\text{Ac}_2\text{O-Py}$. The diacetyl tangulic acid was purified by passing the chloroform solution through a column of alumina and eluting with chloroform-methanol (9:1). First two fractions were discarded and the latter fractions upon crystallisation from methanol gave pure diacetyl tangulic acid XIII, m.p. 272-74°, $[\alpha]_D -15^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in alc.). Found: C, 67.65, H, 8.28 $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_9$ requires C, 67.75 and H, 8.36%. IR: 3560 (OH); 1735-25, 1250 (acetate); 1705-1695 (COOH);

1650, 850 and 808 $\left(\begin{array}{c} \text{H} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{C}=\text{C} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \end{array} \right) \text{cm}^{-1}$. ^1H NMR in d_6 -DMSO at 100 MHz in δ -values: 5.16m (12-H), 5.64m (2 β -H), 4.68, 4.78d J=10 Hz (3 α -H), 2.00 and 1.95s (2 α , 3 β -OCOCH₃, 0.70, 0.86, 0.94, 1.06, 1.14 and 1.30s (six CH₂). Mass: M⁺, 602(2); M-H₂O, 584(1); M-HCOOH, 556(5); M-HCOOH-AcOH, 496(75); RDA fragments at 264(15) and 338(10).

Compound XII acetate (100 mg) was refluxed with 4% alcoholic KOH (35 ml) for 4 hr. Usual working up gave compound XII as colourless prisms from methanol (50 mg), m.p. 310-12°, $[\alpha]_D +35^\circ$ (c, 0.8 in alc.). Found: C, 69.37; H, 8.92 $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 69.47 and H, 8.94%. IR: 3560, 3450 br (OH);

1710, 1695 (COOH); 1650, 856 and 808 $\left(\begin{array}{c} \text{H} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{C}=\text{C} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \end{array} \right) \text{cm}^{-1}$.

Dimethyl tangulate (CH₂N₂/ether): The dimethyl-ester crystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m. p. 226-28°, $[\alpha]_D +32^\circ$ (c, 0.6 in EtOH). Found: C, 70.18; H, 9.16 $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 70.30 and H, 9.22%. IR: 3560, 3450 br (OH); 1735, 1255 (ester); 1650 848 and 810 $\left(\begin{array}{c} \text{H} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{C}=\text{C} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \end{array} \right) \text{cm}^{-1}$.

Diacetyldimethyl tangulate (XVI): (Diacetate-CH₂N₂/ether) The dimethylester diacetate crystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m. p. 168-69°, $[\alpha]_D +5^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in MeOH). Found: C, 68.46; H, 8.5 $\text{C}_{63}\text{H}_{84}\text{O}_9$ requires C, 68.55 and H, 8.63%. IR: 3560 (OH); 1745-25, 1250 (esters). ^1H NMR in CDCl_3 at 60 MHz in δ -values: 5.30m (12-H); 5.42m (2 β -H); 4.88, 5.05d J=10 Hz (3 α -H); 2.65bs (18-OH); 3.64s, 3.76s (23, 28-COCH₃); 2.10s, 2.05s (2 α , 3 β -OCOCH₃); 0.717, 0.96, 1.25 and 1.30 (six CH₂). Mass: M-COOMe, 571(5); RDA fragment a-278(30); a-H₂O-COOMe, 201(60); b 352(40); b-2AcOH-COOMe, 173(80).

Acutangulic acid (III): Compound III was purified through its acetate. The crude acetate was run over a column of silica gel and eluted with a mixture of chloroform-acetone (95:5). Latter fractions

crystallised from benzene-acetone and the pure acetate was obtained as colourless shining needles, m.p. 189-90°, $[\alpha]_D -35^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in chloroform). Found: C, 71.07; H, 9.08 $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 71.30 and H, 9.15%. IR: 3540 (OH); 1740-25, 1250 (acetate); 1695 (COOH);

1650 and 860 $\left(\begin{array}{c} \text{H} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{C}=\text{C} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \end{array} \right) \text{cm}^{-1}$. ^1H NMR in CDCl_3 at 60 MHz in δ -values: 5.42m (12-H); 5.05, 5.12, 5.20, 5.28d/d J=4, 9 Hz (2 β -H); 4.78, 4.93d J=9 Hz (3 α -H); 2.60bs (18-OH) (partially exchanges with D₂O); 2.00s, 2.08s (2 α , 3 β -OCOCH₃); 0.75, 0.93, 0.98, 1.10, 1.20 and 1.28 (seven CH₂). Mass: M⁺, 572(8); M-H₂O, 554(5); M-HCOOH, 526(50); R.D.A. fragment a, 264(50); a-H₂O, 246.(75); a-H₂O-COOH, 201(100); fragment b, 308(5); b-2AcOH, 188(65).

The acetate (100 mg) was refluxed with 4% alc. KOH (25 ml) on a steam bath for 4 hr. The product crystallised from methanol as colourless tiny needles of pure acutangulic acid (50 mg), m. p. 289-90° $[\alpha]_D +15^\circ$ (c, 0.6 in EtOH). L. B. positive, yellow colour with tetranitromethane. Found: C, 73.63; H, 9.72 $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 73.73 and H, 9.9%. IR: 3550, 3400br (OH); 1710-1695 (COOH);

1650, 856, 808 $\left(\begin{array}{c} \text{H} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{C}=\text{C} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \end{array} \right) \text{cm}^{-1}$.

Methyl acutangulate: (CH₂N₂/ether) The methyl ester crystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m. p. 250-52° $[\alpha]_D +13^\circ$ (c, 0.8 in EtOH). Found: C, 73.96; H, 10.00 $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 74.06 and H, 10.02%. IR: 3540, 3400br (OH); 1735, 1250 (ester); 1650, 852 and 806 cm^{-1} .

Diacetylmethyl acutangulate (VIII): (The diacetate-CH₂N₂/ether). The methylester acetate crystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m. p. 219-20°, $[\alpha]_D -8^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in CHCl_3). Found: C, 71.44; H, 9.18 $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 71.64 and H, 9.28%. IR: 3540 (OH); 1745-25, 1265 (ester); 1650 and 850 cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR in CDCl_3 at 60 MHz in δ -values: 5.43m (12-H); 5.00m (2 β -H); 4.83, 4.68d J=10 Hz (3 α -H); 2.68bs (18-OH); (exchanges partially with D₂O), 3.67s (28-COCH₃); 2.08s, 2.00s (2 α , 3 β -OCOCH₃); 0.68, 0.93, 1.1, 1.23 and 1.27 (seven CH₂). Mass: M⁺, 586(15); M-H₂O, 568(25); M-2AcOH, 466(40); RDA fragment a, 278(80); a-H₂O, 260(90); a-H₂O-COOMe 201(100); fragment b, 308(10); b-2AcOH, 188(75).

Barringtonic acid (II): Compound I crystallised from methanol as prisms, m.p. 320-30°. It was purified through its dimethylester, m. p. 253-54° $[\alpha]_D +61^\circ$. Found: C, 72.10; H, 9.38 $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 72.40 and H, 9.50%.

The dimethylester diacetate: (Ac₂O + Py/100°/2 h.) The resulting acetate crystallised as shining needles from methanol, m. p. 238-40°, undepressed by admixture with an authentic sample of diacetyldimethyl barringtonate, $[\alpha]_D +34^\circ$ (c, 0.4 in MeOH).

Oxidation of diacetyl acutangulic acid 11-keto acutangulic acid (XIa): a) Diacetyl acutangulic acid (100 mg) in dry pure pyridine (8 ml) was added to Py-CrO_3 (100 ml containing 100 mg of CrO_3) at room temperature and kept overnight. The starting compound was recovered unchanged.

b) Diacetyl acutangulic acid (50 mg) in dry aldehyde-free acetic acid (8 ml) was reacted with Jones' reagent (10 ml) at room temp for 30 min. and worked up as usual. The product crystallised from benzene as colourless shining needles, (18 mg) m. p. 220°. Found: C, 69.52; H, 8.56 $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 69.60 and H, 8.59%. IR: 3540 (OH); 1745, 1250 (acetate); 1695 (COOH); 1650 (α : β -unsaturated six membered ring ketone) cm^{-1} , UV: 258 (4.20) nm.

Preparation of 11-keto diacetylmethyl acutangulate IX: a) Diacetyl methyl acutangulate (40 mg) was dissolved in aldehyde free acetone (15 ml) and treated with Jones' reagent in excess. The product crystallised from methanol as shining needles, (15 mg) m.p. 165-68°. Found: C, 69.85; H, 8.70 $\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 69.97 and H, 8.72%. IR: 1745-25, 1250 (ester); 1655 (α : β -unsaturated six membered ring ketone) cm^{-1} . UV: 256 (4.23) nm.

b) The 11-keto diacetyl acutangulic acid obtained in the previous experiment was treated with excess ethereal CH_2N_2 and the product crystallised from methanol as colourless tiny crystals, m.p. 166-68°. undepressed by mixing with the sample obtained by method (a).

Diacetylmethyl anhydroacutangulate(X): a) Diacetyl methyl acutangulate (100 mg) in dry pyridine (5 ml) was treated dropwise with freshly redistilled POCl_3 (2 ml). The solution was first heated on a steam-bath for 1 hr. and then refluxed on an oil bath for 3 hr. The solution was cooled and poured carefully onto crushed ice. Diacetylmethyl anhydroacutangulate separated was purified over a column of alumina (50 mg) undepressed by an authentic sample of diacetyl methyl anhydroarjunate (from arjunic acid of *Terminalia arjuna*), m.p. 180-83°, $[\alpha]_D - 116^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in CHCl_3). Found: C, 73.81; H, 9.18 $\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 73.91 and H, 9.21%. IR: 1745-25, 1250 (esters); 860 cm^{-1} . UV: 240 (4.20) nm and 252 nm (sh).

b) Diacetyl methyl acutangulate (50 mg) was dissolved in glacial AcOH (10 ml) 1N H_2SO_4 (10 drops) added and heated on a steam bath for 1 hr. and then refluxed for another hour. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into cold water (100 ml) and the product was extracted with ether. The dried ether extract was evaporated and the residue crystallised from methanol as colourless crystals, m.p. 180-83°, undepressed with the sample prepared by method (a).

Isomerisation of diacetylmethyl anhydroacutangulate to diacetyl methyl dehydromaslinic acid: Anhydro-methyl ester diacetate (50 mg) in CHCl_3 (30 ml) was treated for 30 min., at room temp. with a stream of dry

HCl. Removal of the solvent in vacuo and recrystallisation of the residue from chloroform-methanol yielded tiny needles (30 mg), m.p. 184-87°, unchanged by admixture with an authentic sample of diacetyldehydromaslinic acid ester, $[\alpha]_D - 163^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in CHCl_3). Found: C, 73.72; H, 9.20 $\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 73.91 and H, 9.21%. UV: 241 (4.12), 252 (4.18) and 260 (4.21) nm.

11-keto diacetyl tangulic acid (XVI): Diacetyl tangulic acid (40 mg) was dissolved in aldehyde-free acetone (20 ml) and treated with Jones' reagent. After 1 hr. at room temp. with occasional shaking, methanol (5 ml) was added to destroy excess reagent. The solution was concentrated to half of its volume, poured into cold water (50 ml) and the product crystallised from acetone-methanol mixture as colourless tiny needles (15 mg), m.p. 260-62° $[\alpha]_D + 15^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in MeOH). Found: C, 66.12; H, 7.80 $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_{10}$ requires C, 66.21 and H, 7.84%. IR: 3540 (OH); 1745-25, 1250 (esters); 1660 (α : β -unsaturated six membered ring ketone); 860 and 808 cm^{-1} . UV: 256 (4.12) nm.

Diacetyldimethyl anhydrotangulate (XVII): Diacetyl tangulic acid (75 mg) in dry pyridine (5 ml) was treated dropwise with freshly redistilled POCl_3 (2 ml). The solution was first warmed on a steam bath for 15 min. and then refluxed over an oil bath for 3 hr. The product was purified by passing over a small column of neutral alumina. It was eluted with benzene: acetone (8:2) and the eluate upon removal of the solvent followed by crystallisation from methanol gave pure sample of diacetylanhydrotangulic acid, m.p. 198-99°. Found: C, 69.78; H, 8.25 $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_8$ requires, C, 69.84 and H, 8.27%. IR: 1745-25, 1250 (acetates); 1710, 1695 (COOH); 1660, 860 and 808 cm^{-1} . UV: 246 nm (4.01).

The methyl ester prepared in the usual way (CH_2N_2) gave colourless tiny prisms (MeOH) of diacetyldimethyl anhydrotangulate (40 mg), m.p. 178-79°, $[\alpha]_D - 108^\circ$ (c, 1.0 in MeOH). Found: C, 70.48; H, 8.49 $\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 70.56 and H, 8.55%. IR: 1745-25, 1250 (esters), 1645 and 860 cm^{-1} . UV: 246 (4.02) nm.

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